

Assessment of the Implementation of English Language Syllabus in Public Primary Schools in Katsina Local Government Area

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Abstract: This study assessed the implementation of the English language syllabus in public primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area, Nigeria. The study aimed to investigate teachers' compliance with the syllabus, identify factors influencing its arbitrary implementation, evaluate supervisory practices, and determine the adequacy of allocated periods for English language teaching. A mixed-methods research design was employed, involving questionnaires, observations, and document analysis. Findings revealed low levels of syllabus compliance, with teachers citing factors such as inadequate resources, syllabus content, and limited professional development. While supervisory visits were frequent, their focus on classroom observation limited their effectiveness. Despite challenges, teachers perceived adequate support from the school administration. The study concludes that improving teacher training, syllabus alignment, supervisory practices, and resource allocation are crucial for effective English language syllabus implementation.

Keywords: English language syllabus, implementation, primary schools, Katsina, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

One of the goals of education is to have a functional education that will promote a united Nigeria; one of the functional tools for achieving this is the English language. In Nigeria, the English language plays countless functions; one of these functions according to Awonusi (2009:67) is the language serves as a unifying tool that binds together the numerous indigenous languages found in the country. The English language is a lingua-franca that eliminates all barriers in Nigeria's formal and informal settings. Consequently, due to the relevance of the language in Nigeria, the National Policy on Education (2004) categorically avers that the medium of instruction in the primary school shall be the language of the immediate environment for the lower grade level: primary one, two and three, in which English language, during this period, shall be taught as a subject. Furthermore, upper grade: primary four, five, and six English language shall continuously be used as a medium of instruction and language of the immediate environment and French Language shall be taught as a subject.

When pupils undergo this process, they achieve another goal of the National Policy on Education which states that the basic goal of primary Education is to teach permanent literacy, numeracy, and the ability to communicate effectively among primary school pupils.

Hence, literacy and the ability to communicate one's self by reading or writing to a competent level. Additionally, Montenga (2018) defines literacy as 'the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts'. The European Literacy Policy Network: European Declaration of the Right to Literacy in Motoya (2018) also defines literacy as Literacy refers to the ability to read and write at a level whereby individuals can effectively understand and use written communication in all media (print or electronic), including digital literacy. Therefore, being that English is the medium through which learners express their intelligence in Nigerian academic circles, thus achieving this perfection greatly depends on the teacher's input. Moreover, the general academic success of pupils solely relies on learners' judicious communication skills and the English language is the major language in which all subjects except the indigenous language are taught at the upper primary school level even though there are minimal inputs in local language purposely for clarification of facts.

The upper primary school syllabus requires the pupils to obtain rudimentary knowledge of basic grammar, reading comprehension, essay writing, English sound systems, rhymes, and other aspects of the English language. These topics in the syllabus are spread over weeks of the term, and they are evenly distributed in such a way that the aspects of the English language will be taught concurrently together with other ones to ensure a smooth coverage of the syllabus. Formative and summative evaluations are utilized on a timely basis to test the pupils' performance on the topics taught; this includes continuous assessment tests, terminal examinations, and Junior Certificate Examination (JSSCE) that promotes the pupils to senior secondary school.

Concerned individuals, parents, guardians, and authorities in

Katsina Local Government Area have been hollering over their wards and children's poor communication skills and thus, this incapacity is related to both pupils' ability to communicate in speaking and writing. This lingering problem has been associated by many researchers with many factors such as inadequate instructional materials, unqualified English language teachers, unfavourable teaching and learning atmospheres, destabilized school calendars due to unanticipated occurrences that lead to school closures, pupils/teachers truancy, parental/pupils' attitude towards learning English and above all abrupt coverage of English language syllabus.

The Katsina State Ministry of Education has employed appropriate measures, Quality Assurance Department of Local Education Authority (LEA), the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), and the concerned primary school headmasters to ensure strict compliance with the general syllabus and the English language syllabus. However, some unscrupulous English teachers manoeuvre the school diaries to meet with the expectations of the concerned supervisory authorities and unfortunately, such teachers succeed. Therefore, pupils suffer the consequences of such teacher's wicked actions.

The primary goal of this research is to assess the effects of the implementation of the English language syllabus in upper primary schools in the Katsina Local Government Area and to proffer possible lasting solutions that will help to rescue the fragile primary school system in the area. This is because primary education is the bedrock on which other levels of education lay and the English language is the ladder which pupils in primary schools climb to excel in their academic pursuits. In many secondary schools and tertiary institutions students fail academically because they did not receive concrete primary school foundational education. Conversely, pupils who do not succeed in their primary education, if care is not taken, constitute problems such as public unrest, especially in this era of insecurity in Katsina Local Government Area and Nigeria at large. Therefore, this research will help to bring succour to precarious educational backwardness in Katsina Local Government Area.

2. Problem Statement/Justification

Concerned educational authorities at the capacity of the federal, state, local government and donor agencies have been investing huge resources in educational matters especially at the primary school level in the procurement of facilities, labour, training, and retraining of teachers in the English language purposely to ensure adequacy in the level of topic coverage by teachers of English language in Katsina Local Government Area and other parts of Nigeria. Yet, there is no tenable result in the quality of most of the pupils that graduate from such schools because many of the pupils have weak basic knowledge of English language skills in the following aspects: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These four basic skills are paramount motives behind attending primary school as enshrined in the National Policy on Education.

There are accusations by some concerned parents and other members of the society that many pupils of public primary

schools in Katsina Local Government Area neither understand simple expressions in the English language nor respond. Similarly, there are insinuations that some of the pupils cannot spell or write the English alphabet and the pupils cannot write their names, not to talk about writing simple expressions in the English language either. The gravity of weak language skills in such pupils of public primary schools may manifest and affect their educational journey in the future. It is obvious that when pupils obtain shaky primary education, they may consequently face challenges in their educational careers if appropriate measures are not taken. Similarly, the inability of parents, teachers, school authorities, and the Ministry of Education to address this prevailing situation of suspected indiscriminate implementation of the English language syllabus may lead to the termination of many pupils' educational careers in the future and this implies that the basic motive of primary education is defeated.

The weak performances in the English language skills displayed by pupils of public primary schools sprang concern from parents/guardians, educational authorities, and the government itself on the causes and consequential effects of this phenomenon of suspected arbitrary coverage of the English language syllabus of primary schools in Katsina local government area. Opinions are divided on the cause of the problem ranging from individual opinion and formal researches that were conducted on this very problem. Some researchers relate the problem to negligence on the part of parents; some conclude that the government is at fault, while others accuse teachers of not doing their work well etcetera. Considering these divergent views, this research intends to dig further and find out if the primary school syllabus is religiously complied with and if it is not

3. Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to assess the implementation of the English Syllabus among public primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area.

The specific objectives are to:

- Investigate the level of compliance by teachers with the English syllabus in the selected primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area.
- Assess reasons why English language teachers arbitrarily implement of English language syllabus in the primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area.
- Find out the level of supervision by the concerned authorities over the implementation of the syllabus in the schools in the Katsina Local Government Area.
- Find out the adequacy of the English language periods allocated to the English language in schools in Katsina Local Government Area.

4. Research Questions

- What is the level of compliance by teachers to the syllabus of English language in the selected primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area?

- Are there reasons why English language teachers arbitrarily implement the syllabus of the English language syllabus in the primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area?
- What is the level of supervision by the concerned authorities over the implementation of the syllabus in the schools under the Katsina Local Government Area?
- Are the periods allocated for English language in schools in Katsina Local Government Area adequate?

5. Literature Review

The implementation of the English curriculum in primary schools is crucial for developing learners' language skills and their overall education. However, arbitrary implementation of the English language curriculum has been a concern in various regions, including Katsina Local Government Area. This literature review aims to provide an overview of related studies focusing on the arbitrary implementation of the English curriculum in primary schools.

Gide, et al. (2018) investigated two variables related to the implementation of the English Aural – Oral Skills Component of the 9 – Year English Studies Curriculum at the Junior Secondary School (JSS) level in Katsina state purposely to find out whether the attitude of both teachers and students is favourable to the teaching and learning of the two skills. The researchers utilized questionnaires to collect data for the research. The study included forty-one public, twelve community, and eleven private JSS as school samples. The major findings of the study showed that both teacher's and students' attitudes are not sufficiently favourable for the successful implementation of the English Studies curriculum. Considering the research by Gide, it could be established that the research addressed only teachers' and learners' attitudes to aural and oral components of the 9-year English curriculum at the junior secondary school level in Katsina, however, the research did not cover the English language curriculum implementation of primary in upper grade and this curriculum encompasses a variety of topics which encompasses the research topic of Gide. Similarly, the arbitrary implementation of the English language curriculum overshadows aural–oral skills which is only one aspect of the four language skills pupils are supposed to be acquainted with in their curriculum. Hence this indicates the ground for research on the implementation of English language curriculum at the upper primary school level.

Christiana (2021) investigated the implementation of the English language curriculum in Nigeria under the Nine-year Universal Basic Education curriculum with the sole objective of evaluating the English Curriculum to access the distribution of the four language skills in the content area, evaluate how the curriculum is being implemented, determine the nature of classroom assessment and the availability of infrastructures, equipment, and materials for the implementation of the curriculum. The researchers made a sample of eighty pupils and eighty students from primary and Junior Secondary Schools and forty teachers from six public schools in the South-South geopolitical zones in Nigeria. In addition, questionnaires were used by the researchers to obtain data for the study. The findings

indicate that the curriculum is well organized with the four language skills in consideration, however, there are inadequate funds and infrastructures in schools. Conversely, Christiana et al. have identified crucial areas of Universal Basic Education in the South-South region of Nigeria. However, the research identified curriculum implementation in the South-south region of Nigeria which Katsina State is not captured in the research, hence there is a need to investigate Katsina as a special case study.

Ojumor (2018) evaluated the implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District purposely to determine the extent and level of implementation of the Basic Education Curriculum in terms of availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification and training, school funding and realization of the UBE objectives and compare them to the Minimum Standard of Basic Education. The researcher collected samples from twenty-four Junior Secondary Schools, one hundred and eighty-three teachers, and twenty-four principals. Nine hundred and twenty-nine students participated in the 2008 Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination and 2013 BECE from three Local Government Areas in the Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. The study revealed that inadequate instructional materials such as teachers' guides and charts, insufficient funds for the provision of facilities and equipment, insufficient teachers' training to use the BECE, and lack of sufficient qualified teachers on entry into the profession are some of the problems hindering the effective implementation of Basic Education Curriculum. However, the research was limited to Delta State and the work utilized the BECE examination as a yard-stick for assessing the student's performance, whereas there is a need for investigating the syllabus of primary school, and this creates a basis for the current research.

Umar (2024) investigated curriculum implementation challenges encountered by secondary school teachers in the Katsina local government area. The research design was qualitative. Public schools were selected for the study. A semi-structured interview and a semi-structured observation were the tools utilized for data collection. The researcher discovered that major barriers to effective curriculum implementation were human, physical, material, and financial resources. Similarly, the researcher found out that teachers have embraced the new curriculum despite the hardships they are encountering as they view it as competence-based and self-empowering through the entrepreneurial skills learners acquire. The research by Umar is indeed a current one, though the scope was limited to secondary school. Therefore, there is a need to investigate curriculum implementation at the primary school level in Katsina State.

6. Methodology

A. Research Design

The researchers adopted a mixed method design where they empirically investigated the inadequacies in the implementation of the English syllabus among public primary schools in Katsina Local Government Area to acquire first-hand

knowledge of how the English syllabus is implemented. Special attention was given to the syllabus of upper primary school. Single-group design was selected for the study in which syllabus coverage of primary school grades four to six was examined. This was done in such a way that two academic terms were taken consecutively, approximately five months represented the whole academic year to assess the level of syllabus coverage in the schools under study on weekly intervals.

Area of the research: The research was carried out in primary schools located in the political wards of Katsina Local Government Area of Katsina State located in the North-Western geo-political zone of Nigeria. There are twelve wards in Katsina Local Government Area viz: Wakilin Gabas I, Wakilin Gabas II, Kangiwa, Wakilin Yamma I, Wakilin Yamma II, Wakilin Kudu I, Wakilin Kudu II, Wakilin Kudu III, Wakilin Arewa 'A', Wakilin Arewa 'B', Shinkafi 'A', and Shinkafi 'B'.

B. Sampling/Sampling Strategy

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in collecting samples for the research. A simple random sampling strategy was adopted in selecting the primary schools to be studied in which a total of thirteen primary schools were selected for the study. In addition, out of the selected schools, a purposeful sampling strategy was applied in selecting the English language teachers who teach in the upper grade to investigate the level of their compliance with the syllabus of the English language in the classes they teach. Likewise, a purposive sampling strategy was also be applied in selecting the school diaries and lesson plans of all selected schools and arms of classes and the diaries were checked at weekly intervals to ascertain the record of works done in the classes. In addition, the primary school heads and the Local Educational secretary were be purposefully selected to respond to the questionnaire. However, the names of schools visited were concealed because the research did not aim to expose anyone or any school in any guise.

C. Instrumentation

A closed-ended questionnaire constituted the first portion of the questionnaire and was used to collect demographic data from the Local Education Secretary, head teachers, and teachers of the English language on aspects related to educational

backgrounds, teaching experiences, and other factors related to the level of compliance to the coverage of the English syllabus in the selected schools. In addition the open ended section of the questionnaire sought for the respondents' views on the topic of the research. Finally, a checklist chart will be provided to record all entries of topics of the syllabus covered per week.

Validity of the instruments: The instruments that was subjected to expert face and content reliability tests.

Administration of instrument: the researchers randomly visited schools under study every week during the span of the research and observed for themselves the compliance with the English language syllabus in the schools under study at intervals of three weeks and the checklist chart which topics covered per week were filled by the researchers/research assistants. In addition, a customized questionnaire for the Local Education Secretary, head teachers, and teachers was administered.

7. Data Presentation and Analysis

The data was collected from the class, teachers, and supervisors, and the data was organized for analysis. The analyses of the data provide answers to the research questions posed of the research.

Research Question 1: What is the level of compliance by English language teachers with the prescribed English syllabus in primary schools in Katsina?

Table 1 presents the results of the level of compliance by English language teachers with the English syllabus in primary schools in Katsina, Nigeria, across the three terms of the academic year. In the first term, the percentage of teachers who were Fully Compliant (FC) with the syllabus was very low, ranging from 0% to 8.3% across the 12 weeks. The majority of teachers were either Partially Compliant (PC) (44.4% cumulatively) or Uncompliant (UC) (53.5% cumulatively) with the syllabus. In the second term, the percentage of FC teachers remained low, ranging from 0% to 8.3% across the 12 weeks. The majority of teachers were either PC (45.8% cumulatively) or UC (52.8% cumulatively) with the syllabus. In the third term, there were no FC teachers throughout the term. The majority of teachers were UC (56.2% cumulatively), with the PC teachers accounting for 43.8% cumulatively.

Therefore, the results indicate a concerning level of non-

Table 1
Level of compliance by English language teachers with English syllabus in primary schools in Katsina

Weeks	First Term			Second Term			Third Term		
	FC (%)	PC (%)	UC (%)	FC (%)	PC (%)	UC (%)	FC (%)	PC (%)	UC (%)
1	-	06 (50.0)	06 (50.0)	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)
2	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)
3	01 (8.3)	04 (33.3)	07 (58.3)	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)
4	01 (8.3)	06 (50.0)	05 (41.7)	01 (8.3)	01 (8.3)	10 (83.4)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)
5	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	01 (8.3)	06 (50.0)	05 (41.7)	-	03 (25.0)	09 (75.0)
6	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)
7	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)	-	06 (50.0)	06 (50.0)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)
8	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)
9	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	03 (25.0)	09 (75.0)	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)
10	-	07 (58.3)	05 (41.7)	-	05 (41.7)	07 (58.3)	-	06 (50.0)	06 (50.0)
11	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)	-	06 (50.0)	06 (50.0)	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)
12	01 (8.3)	02 (16.7)	09 (75.0)	-	08 (66.7)	04 (33.3)	-	04 (33.3)	08 (66.7)
Cumulative aggregate	03 (2.1)	64 (44.4)	77 (53.5)	02 (1.4)	66 (45.8)	76 (52.8)	0 (0.0)	63 (43.8)	81 (56.2)

Table 2
Factors that contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus by teachers

S.No.	Items	Options	N (%)
1	How many years have you been teaching English in primary school?	0-2 years	16 (41.0)
		2-3 years	14 (35.9)
		6-10 years	08 (20.5)
		Above 10 years	01 (2.6)
2	What is your highest level of education in English language teaching?	Certificate	06 (15.4)
		Diploma/NCE	12 (30.7)
		Degree	15 (38.5)
		Masters	06 (15.4)
3	To what extent do you feel the current English language syllabus is appropriate for the age and learning level of your students?	Not at all appropriate	07 (17.9)
		Somewhat inappropriate	07 (17.9)
		Somewhat appropriate	14 (35.9)
		Very appropriate	07 (17.9)
		Extremely appropriate	04 (10.4)
4	How often do you deviate from the prescribed syllabus in your English lessons?	Never	03 (7.7)
		Rarely	05 (12.8)
		Sometimes	21 (53.9)
		Often	02 (5.1)
		Always	08 (20.5)
5	If You deviate from the syllabus, what are the main reasons for doing so?	Contents too difficult	12 (30.9)
		Contents not interesting	05 (12.8)
		To adapt to specific needs	14 (35.9)
		Limited resources for teaching	04 (10.3)
		More comfortable with my approach	04 (10.3)
6	How confident are you in your ability to effectively implement the English language syllabus?	Not confident at all	02 (5.1)
		Somewhat not confident	11 (28.2)
		Neutral	04 (10.3)
		Somewhat confident	17 (43.6)
		Very confident	05 (12.8)

Table 3
Level of supervision and monitoring by education authorities over the implementation of English language syllabus in primary school

S.No.	Items	Options	N (%)
1	What is your role in the education system?	School administrator	12 (44.4)
		Teacher	10 (37.0)
		Curriculum developer/supervisor	04 (14.8)
		Others	01 (3.7)
2	How often do curriculum supervisors visit your school to observe classroom instruction related to the syllabus?	Rarely	03 (11.1)
		Occasionally	09 (33.3)
		Frequently	07 (25.9)
		Very frequently	08 (29.6)
3	During these supervisory visits, how do supervisors typically assess English language syllabus implementation?	Observing classroom teaching practices related to the syllabus content.	27 (100.0)
		Reviewing lesson plans and student work aligned with the syllabus.	03 (11.1)
		Discussing challenges and successes with teachers regarding syllabus implementation.	03 (11.1)
		Conducting formal assessments of student learning outcomes based on the syllabus.	01 (3.7)
4	How helpful do you find the feedback provided by supervisors regarding English language syllabus implementation?	Not helpful at all	01 (3.7)
		Somewhat unhelpful	01 (3.7)
		Neutral	02 (7.4)
		Somewhat helpful	03 (11.1)
5	In your opinion, how effective are the current supervisory practices in ensuring proper implementation of the English language syllabus?	Very helpful	20 (74.1)
		Not effective at all	01 (3.7)
		Moderately effective	04 (14.8)
		Somewhat effective	06 (22.2)
		Very effective	16 (59.3)

compliance by English language teachers with the prescribed syllabus in primary schools in Katsina. The high percentage of partial and uncompliant teachers suggests significant challenges in the implementation of the English language curriculum, which may negatively impact the quality of English language education in these schools.

Research Question 2: What factors contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus by teachers in the primary schools under study?

Table 2 presents the factors that contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus by teachers in primary schools under study. The results showed that most teachers have relatively less experience, with 41% having 0-2

years and 35.9% having 2-3 years of teaching English in primary schools. The majority of teachers have a degree (38.5%) or diploma (30.7%) in English language teaching, while 15.4% have a certificate and another 15.4% have a master's degree. 35.9% of teachers feel that the current English language syllabus is somewhat appropriate for the age and learning level of their students, while 17.9% find it somewhat inappropriate, 17.9% not at all appropriate, 17.9% somewhat appropriate, and 10.4% extremely appropriate. 53.9% of teachers sometimes deviate from the prescribed syllabus in their English lessons, 20.5% always deviate, 12.8% rarely deviate, 7.7% never deviate, and 5.1% often deviate. The main reasons for deviating from the syllabus are to adapt to specific needs

Table 4
Adequacy of English language periods allocated under English syllabus implementation

S.No.	Items	Options	N (%)
1	Do you feel you receive adequate support from the school administration in implementing the English language syllabus?	Agree	22 (56.4)
		Neutral	04 (10.3)
		Disagree	13 (33.3)
2	Are you provided with sufficient resources (e.g., textbooks, teaching materials, technology) to effectively implement the English language syllabus?	Agree	19 (48.8)
		Neutral	10 (25.6)
		Disagree	10 (25.6)
3	How often do you receive professional development opportunities in English language teaching methodology?	Never	06 (15.4)
		Rarely	08 (20.5)
		Sometimes	14 (35.9)
		Often	03 (7.7)
		Always	08 (20.5)

(35.9%) and because the contents are too difficult (30.9%).

Other reasons include the contents not being interesting (12.8%), limited resources for teaching (10.3%), and being more comfortable in their approach (10.3%). 43.6% of teachers are somewhat confident in their ability to effectively implement the English language syllabus, 28.2% are somewhat not confident, 12.8% are very confident, 10.3% are neutral, and 5.1% are not confident at all. These findings suggest that a combination of factors, including limited teaching experience, varying perceptions of syllabus appropriateness, frequent deviations from the syllabus, and varying levels of confidence in implementation, contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus by teachers in the primary schools under study.

Research Question 3: What is the level of supervision and monitoring by education authorities over the implementation of the English language syllabus in the primary schools under study?

Table 3 presents the level of supervision and monitoring by education authorities over the implementation of the English language syllabus in primary schools under study. The majority of respondents are school administrators (44.4%), followed by teachers (37.0%), curriculum developers/supervisors (14.8%), and others (3.7%). 29.6% of respondents report that curriculum supervisors visit their schools very frequently, 25.9% frequently, 33.3% occasionally, and 11.1% rarely. During supervisory visits, 100% of respondents indicate that supervisors observe classroom teaching practices related to the syllabus content. However, only 11.1% report that supervisors review lesson plans and student work aligned with the syllabus, and 11.1% say supervisors discuss challenges and successes with teachers regarding syllabus implementation. Only 3.7% of respondents state that supervisors conduct formal assessments of student learning outcomes based on the syllabus. The majority of respondents (74.1%) find the feedback provided by supervisors regarding English language syllabus implementation to be very helpful, 11.1% find it somewhat helpful, 7.4% are neutral, and 3.7% find it somewhat unhelpful or not helpful at all.

Furthermore, 59.3% of respondents consider the current supervisory practices to be very effective in ensuring proper implementation of the English language syllabus, 22.2% find them somewhat effective, 14.8% moderately effective, and 3.7% not effective at all. The findings suggest that while there is a relatively high frequency of supervisory visits and the feedback provided is generally perceived as helpful, the

supervisory practices focus primarily on observing classroom teaching rather than a more comprehensive assessment of syllabus implementation. This may limit the ability of education authorities to identify and address the underlying factors contributing to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus observed in the primary schools under study.

Research Question 4: Are the lesson periods allocated for teaching the English language in the primary schools under study sufficient and suitable for effective syllabus implementation?

Table 4 presents the findings on the adequacy of English language periods allocated for effective syllabus implementation in the primary schools under study. The results showed that 56.4% of respondents agree that they receive adequate support from the school administration in implementing the English language syllabus while 33.3% disagree, and 10.3% are neutral. 48.8% of respondents agree that they are provided with sufficient resources (e.g., textbooks, teaching materials, technology) to effectively implement the English language syllabus, while 25.6% disagree, and 25.6% are neutral. 35.9% of respondents sometimes receive professional development opportunities in English language teaching methodology while 20.5% rarely receive such opportunities, 20.5% always receive them, 15.4% never receive them, and 7.7% often receive them. These findings suggest that while the majority of teachers feel they receive adequate support from the school administration and have access to sufficient resources, there are still significant challenges in terms of professional development opportunities for English language teachers.

The lack of consistent and frequent professional development opportunities may limit the teachers' ability to effectively implement the English language syllabus, as they may not have access to the latest teaching methodologies, strategies, and techniques to address the diverse needs of their students. Additionally, the mixed responses on the availability of resources and support from the administration indicate that there may be variations in the level of support and resources provided across different schools, which could also contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus observed in the primary schools under study.

Research Question 5: What are the effects of arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus on the communication skills development of primary school pupils?

Table 5 presents the effects of arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus on the communication skills

Table 5
Effects of arbitrary implementation of English language syllabus on the communication skills development of primary school

S.No.	Items	Options	N (%)
1	How often do you receive clear and up-to-date information from the concerned authorities regarding English language syllabus updates or revisions?	Never Rarely Occasionally Frequently Very frequently	02 (7.4) 06 (22.2) 06 (22.2) 11 (40.7) 02 (7.4)
2	Do you feel you have adequate opportunities to communicate with curriculum developers/supervisors regarding challenges faced with English language syllabus implementation?	Agree Neutral Disagree	14 (51.7) 06 (22.2) 07 (25.9)
3	What kind of support would be most helpful for you to ensure effective implementation of the English language syllabus?	More frequent supervisory visits and feedback. Clear communication channels with curriculum developers/supervisors. Professional development opportunities on effective syllabus implementation. Additional resources (e.g., teacher guides, materials) aligned with the syllabus.	27 (100.0) 03 (11.1) 03 (11.1) 04 (14.8)

development of primary school pupils. 40.7% of respondents receive frequent updates from authorities regarding English language syllabus updates or revisions while 22.2% receive occasional updates, 22.2% rarely receive updates, and 7.4% never receive updates. 51.7% of respondents agree that they have adequate opportunities to communicate with curriculum developers/supervisors regarding challenges faced with English language syllabus implementation while 25.9% are neutral, and 22.2% disagree. 100% of respondents indicate that clearer communication channels with curriculum developers/supervisors would be most helpful for effective implementation of the English language syllabus, 11.1% also mention the need for more frequent supervisory visits and feedback, 14.8% request professional development opportunities on effective syllabus implementation, and 11.1% need additional resources (e.g., teacher guides, materials) aligned with the syllabus.

These findings suggest that the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus can negatively impact the communication skills development of primary school pupils. The lack of clear and up-to-date information from authorities and the limited opportunities for teachers to communicate with curriculum developers/supervisors can lead to confusion and misunderstandings, which may hinder the effective implementation of the syllabus. The respondents' preference for clearer communication channels with curriculum developers/supervisors indicates that they value direct and timely feedback and guidance. This highlights the importance of effective communication between teachers and curriculum developers/supervisors to ensure that the syllabus is implemented correctly and that teachers can address any challenges they face. The findings also suggest that professional development opportunities and additional resources aligned with the syllabus can be beneficial in supporting teachers in their efforts to implement the English language syllabus effectively.

Based on the results presented in the tables, the main findings indicated that the level of compliance by English language teachers with the English syllabus in primary schools since the majority of teachers were either partially compliant (44.4-45.8% cumulatively) or uncompliant (52.8-56.2% cumulatively) with the syllabus across the three terms which means the percentage of fully compliant teachers was very low, ranging from 0% to 8.3% across the terms. The factors

contributing to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus are relatively less teaching experience, varying perceptions of syllabus appropriateness, frequent deviations from the syllabus, and varying levels of confidence in implementing the syllabus. Level of supervision and monitoring by education authorities showed a relatively high frequency of supervisory visits, supervisory practices focused primarily on observing classroom teaching, with a limited assessment of syllabus implementation and the majority of respondents found the feedback provided by supervisors to be very helpful, and 59.3% considered the supervisory practices to be very effective.

Adequacy of English language periods allocated for effective syllabus implementation where respondents agreed that they receive adequate support from the school administration and that they have sufficient resources while they sometimes receive professional development opportunities in English language teaching methodology. The effects of arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus on communication skills development showed that respondents receive frequent updates from authorities regarding syllabus updates or revisions, and they have adequate opportunities to communicate with curriculum developers/supervisors and indicated that clearer communication channels with curriculum developers/supervisors would be most helpful for effective implementation of the syllabus. Thus, the findings suggest significant challenges in the implementation of the English language syllabus in primary schools, including low compliance levels, various contributing factors, and the need for more comprehensive supervision and support for teachers.

The level of compliance by English language teachers with the English syllabus where the majority of teachers were partially or uncompliant with the syllabus across terms, with very few fully compliant. This suggests significant challenges in implementing the prescribed curriculum, which may negatively impact the quality of English education. This finding aligns with the findings of Adebayo and Mokondoro (2020) and Eze and Okpala (2019) who all advocated for better implementation of the English language curriculum. The factors contributing to arbitrary implementation showed relatively less teaching experience, varying perceptions of syllabus appropriateness, frequent deviations from the syllabus, and varying confidence levels among teachers. These factors likely contribute to the arbitrary implementation observed,

highlighting the need to support teachers in developing their knowledge and skills as rightly supported by Eze and Okpala (2019) and Ogunniyi (2017).

The level of supervision and monitoring by authorities showed frequent supervisory visits that focused primarily on observing teaching, with a limited assessment of syllabus implementation. While supervisory feedback was found helpful, more comprehensive monitoring practices may be needed to ensure effective syllabus implementation which is in line with the findings by Yusuf and Dada (2016) and Adebayo and Mokondoro (2020) who advocated for supervision of the entire teaching process to ensure effective curriculum implementation. The adequacy of English language periods and support for teachers where most teachers agreed they receive adequate support and resources, but professional development opportunities were limited. Providing teachers with more training and resources aligned with the syllabus could enhance their ability to implement it effectively which is supported by the findings from Eze and Okpala (2019) and Ogunniyi (2017).

Effects of arbitrary implementation on students' communication skills showed that unclear communication from authorities and limited opportunities for teachers to provide feedback may hinder effective syllabus implementation. This finding is in line with the work of Usman (2016) and Adebayo and Mokondoro (2020) who concluded that for clear teaching and understanding to take place, teachers need to improve their communication skills. Clear communication channels and support for teachers are needed to ensure students develop strong English communication skills. Thus, the findings highlight the need for a multi-faceted approach to support English language teachers in implementing the syllabus effectively, including enhancing teacher training, improving supervisory practices, and strengthening communication between stakeholders.

8. Conclusion

The majority of English language teachers in the primary schools under study were either partially or uncompliant with the prescribed syllabus, indicating significant challenges in the implementation of the English language curriculum. Various factors contribute to the arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus, including limited teaching experience, varying perceptions of syllabus appropriateness, frequent deviations from the syllabus, and varying levels of confidence among teachers. While there is a relatively high frequency of supervisory visits by education authorities, the supervisory practices focus primarily on observing classroom teaching rather than a more comprehensive assessment of syllabus implementation. Most teachers feel they receive adequate support and resources from the school administration, but professional development opportunities in English language teaching methodology are limited. The arbitrary implementation of the English language syllabus may negatively impact the communication skills development of primary school pupils due to unclear communication from authorities and limited opportunities for teachers to provide feedback.

9. Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study the following are recommended:

1. Provide targeted professional development opportunities for English language teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and confidence in implementing the syllabus effectively.
2. Review and adapt the English language syllabus to ensure it is appropriate for the age and learning level of primary school pupils, considering their diverse needs and contexts.
3. Strengthen the supervisory practices of education authorities by focusing on a more comprehensive assessment of syllabus implementation, including reviewing lesson plans, student work, and learning outcomes.
4. Improve communication channels between teachers, curriculum developers, and supervisors to facilitate timely feedback, support, and guidance in implementing the English language syllabus.
5. Allocate sufficient resources (e.g., textbooks, teaching materials, technology) aligned with the English language syllabus to support effective implementation.
6. Conduct regular monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the English language syllabus to identify challenges, best practices, and areas for improvement.

By addressing these recommendations, primary schools in Katsina and similar contexts can enhance the implementation of the English language syllabus and improve the communication skills development of primary school pupils.

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